

Joanna Page, Professor of Latin American Studies, Director of CRASSH, University of Cambridge

Open access breaks down barriers

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Geography and wealth should not determine who has access to research and knowledge. Open access breaks down barriers, making research and knowledge available to all.

Knowledge should be democratised, freely available to people everywhere. That is what a lot of academics think. It's certainly what Joanna Page, Professor of Latin American Studies at the University of Cambridge, and Director of CRASSH (Centre for Research in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences) thinks. She said:

“ We need to think about what happens to knowledge globally. We should be aiming to create a system that is equitable on a global level.

Current barriers to access

Many academics, individuals, libraries and other institutions in Latin America struggle to access important research and knowledge because of the cost of academic books and subscription fees.

Page's research involves collaborating with academics and artists in Latin America, so for her, it is vital that they can access the research she produces. If she hadn't published open access, those academics and artists would have been denied

access to the research output. She thinks it would also have damaged her professional reputation in Latin American academic circles.

She said:

“There’s a very strong ground level feeling that scholarship should be accessible and free in Latin America.”

Greater reader numbers

Publishing open access has enabled Page to reach a much broader audience, in Latin America and beyond. When she posted her latest open access book on her social media channels, her Latin American collaborators picked it up and distributed it among their networks.

Page said:

“This really pushed it out to different markets. From what I’ve seen, individuals with large networks sharing on social media can be just as effective, if not more effective than the distribution processes of traditional presses.”

Quicker publication

Although the process was just as rigorous as with traditional publishing, and the output just as professional, Page says the open presses she has published with work in very agile ways. This has expedited publication times, which is important to Page because her work is on contemporary artists, so she likes her research to be available as quickly as possible.

Paying for open access

When Page first looked into publishing open access, it was easier to find a publisher that would foot the bill than she had expected. Some presses don’t advertise that they publish open access, while others are running pilot schemes or are prepared to waive fees on a case-by-case basis. Page says it’s important that academics look around and ask for opportunities.

But she is also concerned that the open access route could lead to new inequalities – rather than paying to access research, people will have to pay to publish it. And just as certain academics, particularly those in the Global South are less likely to

have the funds to access research, they are less likely to have the funds to pay to publish. Page said:

“ To create a more fully democratic access to knowledge across the world, we would also need to ensure that authors in other countries can not only read but also publish without having to pay.